

ACRIDINES AS ANTISEPTICS

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Certain 5-(diethylamino-alkyl)-aminoacridines have been prepared. Their basicity as well as the antiseptic properties have been recorded.

Since the observations of Browning (*J. Path. & Bact.*, 1914, 18, 144), the salts of 2:8-diaminoacridines are being largely used as antiseptics. But they are often more toxic to leucocytes than to bacteria, become inactivated by absorption on cotton-dressings, and are found to cause sloughing in wounds on prolonged application. Recently, 2:7-diamino- and 5-amino-acridines have, however, been found to be somewhat free from the above drawbacks (*cf.* Albert *et. al.*, *Quart. J. Pharm. & Pharmacol.*, 1937, 10, 649; Rubbo *et al.*, *Brit. J. Path. & Bact.*, 1942, 23, 69).

Accordingly a systematic study on various 5-(diethylamino-alkyl)-aminoacridine derivatives is being made in this laboratory for the last few years (Basu and Bose, *Annal. Biochem & Exp. Med.*, 1941, 1, 317; Bose *et al.*, *Ind. Med. Gaz.*, 1944, 79, 595, 601). These compounds are strong bases and as Albert has noticed that the bactericidal action of the acridine derivatives is associated with their basicity (*Nature*, 1941, 147, 332), an investigation was undertaken to study the bactericidal properties of various 5-(dialkylamino-alkyl)-aminoacridines prepared in this laboratory. In the meantime Lawrence and his collaborators (*J. Lab. Clin. Med.*, 1944, 29, 134, 1177) have noticed a strong bactericidal action in certain acridine derivatives of the above type. The investigations that have been so far carried out are being recorded in this paper.

Diethylamino-ethyl, -propyl, - β -hydroxypropyl, -butyl, -isoamyl amines have been condensed with 5-chloroacridine to afford 5-(diethylamino-ethyl), 5-(γ -diethylamino-propyl)-, 5-(γ -diethylamino- β -hydroxypropyl)-, 5(δ -diethylaminobutyl)-, and 5-(*m*-diethylamino-isoamyl) aminoacridines. The basicity and the bactericidal properties of all these compounds have been studied. Besides, 2-chloro-7-methoxy-5-(δ -diethylamino butyl)-aminoacridine (*cf.* Basu and Bose, *loc. cit.*) was obtained by reacting the 5-chloroacridine derivative with δ -diethylamino-butylamine and tested for its basicity as well as bactericidal property. 2-Aminothiazole was also condensed with 5-chloroacridine, but the condensation product was found to possess no special bactericidal property.

Fig. 1

In the graph are shown the potentiometric titration curves of the dihydrochlorides of diethylamino-butyl- (3), -propyl-(5), -isoamyl-(4), - β -hydroxypropyl-(7), -ethyl-(3), aminoacridines respectively and also of 2-chloro-7-methoxy-5- δ -diethylaminoacridine dihydrochloride (6) against alkali. The curves for proflavin (1) and 5-aminoacridine (2) (Albert, *loc. cit.*) are also included for comparison. Approximately 0.002 g. mole of crystalline hydrochloride in each case was dissolved in 25 c.c. of 50% ethanol and titrated against 0.5N-NaOH using hydrogen electrode in a titration cell having all-glass ground-in joints. The hydrogen used was electrolytically generated and carefully purified in the usual manner.

The acidity constants (pK_a), calculated from the curves are shown in Table I whence the basicity of the various derivatives would be easily noticed. It is evident that the 5-(diethylamino-alkyl)-aminoacridines are quite as basic as 5-aminoacridine. The antibacterial activity of this group of compounds would be evident from Table II.

Further work is in progress to study the influence of various nuclear substitutes on the basicity and consequently on the bactericidal property 5-aminoacridines.

TABLE I

No.	Compound.	Solubility of the dihydrochloride in 95% ethanol at 33° (room temp.)	pH of the dihydrochloride in water		pK _a
			1% soln.	2% soln.	
1	Proflavine	—	—	—	9.5 (Albert)
2	5-Aminoacridine	—	—	—	9.34 (Albert)
8	5-(Diethylaminoethylamino)-acridine	1 in 30	5.3	5.1	7.35
5	5-(Diethylaminopropylamino)-acridine	1 in 11	5.8	5.5	8.6
3	5-(Diethylaminobutylamino)-acridine	1 in 11	5.8	5.5	8.6
4	5-(<i>α</i> -Diethylamino- <i>iso</i> -amylamino)-acridine	1 in 14	6.1	5.8	8.3
7	5-(<i>γ</i> -Diethylamino- <i>β</i> -hydroxypropylamino)acridine	1 in 100	5.4	5.3	7.6
6	2-Chloro-7-methoxy-5-(<i>δ</i> -diethylaminobutylamino)-acridine	1 in 150	4.9	4.5	8.2

TABLE II

Bacteriostatic property

Minimal inhibiting concentration in mg. of the compound per 100 c.c. of culture media

Serial Number.	Compound.	Staphylo aureus.	Streptococcal (Haemo).	B. Coli.	Proteus.	Pyocyanus.
1.	Acriflavine	1	0.2	2	10	20
2.	5-Aminoacridine	2	1	2	2	10
4.	<i>iso</i> Amyl "	10	0.5	20	50	100
3.	Butyl "	2	0.2	4	10	20
5.	Propyl "	2	0.2	2	4	10
7.	Hydroxy-propyl	4	1	4	20	50
8.	Ethyl "	10	2	10	50	100
6.	Compound 6	1	0.2	4	50	50

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

5-(Diethylaminoethyl)-aminocridine Hydrochloride.—5-Chloroacridine (2 g.) was dissolved in phenol (10 c.c.) at 100-110° and diethylaminoethylamine (1 g.) was dropped into it with stirring during the course of $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, and the mixture heated at the same temperature for about 2 hours more. It was cooled and diluted with benzene. The mixture was made alkaline with sodium hydroxide and shaken in a separating funnel. The benzene solution obtained was treated with dilute acetic acid and the

whole thing extracted repeatedly with water. The aqueous solution was basified with dilute ammonia and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried with potassium carbonate and dry hydrogen chloride passed through it whereby the dihydrochloride of 5-(diethylaminoethyl)-aminoacridine was obtained as yellow crystals. The solid isolated was recrystallised from a mixture of acetone and alcohol, m.p. 249-50°. (Found: N, 11.3; Cl, 18.7; H₂O, 4.3. C₁₉H₂₇N₃, 2HCl, H₂O requires N, 10.9; Cl, 18.5; H₂O, 4.68 per cent). The dihydrochloride is highly soluble in water, and an 1% solution of it is not salted out of normal saline. On keeping with sodium citrate solution, however, a crystalline precipitate, m.p. 350°, separates out. The base liberated by adding dilute ammonia to the hydrochloride solution is a viscous semi-solid mass forming a picrate, m. p. 205°. [Found: N, 17.0. C₁₉H₂₇N₃, 2C₆H₅(OH)(NO₂)₂ requires N, 16.8 per cent]. Auric chloride compound, m. p. 120° (indifferently). (Found: Au, 41.0. C₁₉H₂₇N₃, 2HAuCl₄ requires Au, 40.5 per cent].

5-(γ-Diethylaminopropyl)-aminoacridine Hydrochloride.—Diethylaminopropylamine (1.3 g.) was reacted with 5-chloroacridine (2.1 g.) in a manner similar to the previous case and the dihydrochloride of 5-(γ-diethylaminopropyl)-aminoacridine isolated in a similar manner. The final product is a yellow crystalline solid, m.p. 230° when crystallised from a mixture of acetone and alcohol, yield 3 g. (Found: N, 10.63; Cl, 17.76; H₂O, 4.52, C₁₈H₂₅N₃, 2HCl, H₂O requires N, 10.5; Cl, 17.83; H₂O, 4.5 per cent).

The dihydrochloride is very soluble in water. The base is a viscous semi-solid mass forming a picrate, m. p. 197°. [Found: N, 16.6. C₁₈H₂₅N₃, 2C₆H₅(OH)(NO₂)₂ requires N, 16.47 per cent].

5-(δ-Diethylaminobutyl)-aminoacridine Hydrochloride.—5-Chloroacridine (2.1 g.) and δ-diethylaminobutylamine (1.4 g.) were reacted together in a manner similar to the previous cases and 5-(δ-diethylaminobutyl)-aminoacridine dihydrochloride isolated as above. The yellow crystals were very soluble in water and melted at 237-38°. (Found: N, 10.36; Cl, 16.7; H₂O, 4.5. C₂₁H₂₇N₃, 2HCl, H₂O requires N, 10.2; Cl, 17.2; H₂O, 4.4 per cent).

The base, liberated by adding ammonia to the hydrochloride solution is a semi-solid viscous mass forming picrate, m. p. 203-204°. [Found: N, 16.3. C₂₁H₂₇N₃, 2C₆H₅(OH)(NO₂)₂ requires N, 16.1 per cent).

The chloroplatinate melts at 200-10° (decomp.). (Found: Pt, 26.5. C₂₁H₂₇N₃, H₂ PtCl₆ requires Pt, 26.7 per cent).

5-(ω-Diethylaminoisoamyl)-aminoacridine Hydrochloride.—5-Chloroacridine (2.1 g.) was reacted as usual with ω-diethylaminoisoamylamine (1.6 g.) in phenol medium and the dihydrochloride of 5-(ω-diethylaminoisoamyl)-aminoacridine isolated as above, m. p. 194°, yield

3 g. It is very soluble in water. (Found: N, 10.19; Cl, 16.5; H₂O, 3.83. C₂₂H₂₀N₄ · 2HCl, H₂O requires N, 9.85; Cl, 16.6 H₂O, 4.2 per cent). The base was obtained as a semi-solid viscous mass which forms a picrate, m. p. 170°. [Found: N, 16.1. C₂₇H₂₆N₈, 2C₆H₅(OH)(NO₂)₂ requires N, 15.9 per cent].

5-(γ-Diethylamino-β-hydroxypropyl)-aminoacridine Hydrochloride.—5-Chloroacridine (2.1 g.) was reacted with γ-diethylamino-β-hydroxypropylamine (1.5 g.) as above and the dihydrochloride of (γ-diethylamino-β-hydroxypropyl)-aminoacridine isolated as usual.

It is a yellow crystalline solid, highly soluble in water and melts at 230°. (Found: N, 10.6; Cl, 17.0; H₂O, 2.3 C₂₆H₂₈O₂N₂ · 2HCl, ½H₂O requires N, 10.4; Cl, 17.5; H₂O, 2.2 per cent).

The base liberated from the hydrochloride solution by dilute ammonia is a solid, m. p. 88-89°.

5-(2'-Aminothiazol)acridine.—5-Chloroacridine (2.1 g.) was taken in 10 c. c. anhydrous phenol and 1. g. of 2-aminothiazole added to it gradually during the course of half an hour, the temperature being maintained at 100-110°. The reaction mixture was heated for 2 hours more. The cold mass was basified with dilute sodium hydroxide in cold and taken in benzene. The benzene solution was treated with dilute acetic acid and the acetic acid solution obtained basified with ammonia whereby the base 5-(2-aminothiazolyl)acridine was obtained as a solid. This was crystallised from dilute alcohol in slender needles, m. p. 235°. (Found: N, 14.9; S, 13.1, C₁₆H₁₁N₃S requires N, 15.15; S, 13.3 per cent).

The base forms a hydrochloride which can be crystallised from dilute alcohol in beautiful needle-shaped crimson-coloured crystals. m. p. 250°. It is sparingly soluble in water.

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